

Physiology and plant nutrition

Integrated organic and inorganic fertilizer for flooded rice in Kerala, India

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Azolla and rice straw are easily available organic fertilizers in Kerala. We studied the effect of inorganic N sources (prilled urea [PU] and urea supergranules [USG]) alone and in combination with azolla (3.24% N, 0.20% P, 1.28% K, and 6.2% dry matter) and rice straw (0.035% N, 0.03% P, 0.59% K, and 58% dry matter) on grain and straw yields of transplanted Jaya during 1986-87 dry season. The 12 treatments were laid out in randomized block design with 4 replications.

Soil of the experimental site is lateritic sandy clay loam with pH 5.5, 0.88% organic C, 2.53 kg available P/ha, 90.42 kg available K/ha, 35.8% coarse sand, 23.6% fine sand, 9.3% silt, and 29.3% clay. In treatments with organic fertilizer, 29 kg N/ha was supplied by organic manure and the rest by inorganic fertilizer. P was applied at 19.65 kg/ha and potash at 37.5 kg K/ha. PU was applied 1/2 as basal and 1/2 at panicle initiation. USGs were placed 10 cm deep at planting.

Grain yields with 58 kg N/ha were statistically the same as with 87 kg N/ha, except that with USG + rice straw (see table). Organic manure can easily replace inorganic fertilizer at each fertilizer level. Yields with PU and USG, alone or with azolla/rice straw, were not significantly different.

Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on grain and straw yields of flooded rice. Kerala India, 1986-87 dry season.

Treatment	Rate (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Control	0	2.0	1.7
PU	58	2.6	2.2
PU + azolla	58	2.4	2.6
PU + rice straw	58	2.4	2.3
USG	58	2.7	2.2
USG + azolla	58	2.4	2.0
USG + rice straw	58	2.5	1.8
PU	87	2.7	2.9
PU + azolla	87	2.3	2.8
PU + rice straw	87	2.6	2.4
USG	87	2.9	2.2
USG + azolla	87	2.9	2.6
USG + rice straw	87	3.2	2.8
LSD (0.05)	—	0.5	0.4

In the case of straw yield, organic material was as good as inorganic fertilizer. Straw yield increased with increased fertilizer, perhaps due to higher vegetative growth in plots fertilized with 87 kg N/ha. □

Effect of phosphorus on growth and rice plant nutrient content

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We studied the effect of 4 levels of P on rice growth and nutrient content in a pot experiment. The alluvial soil had pH 7.8, 0.63% organic C, EC 0.12%, CEC 14.25 meq/100 g soil, 0.069% total N, 0.094% total P, 3.9 ppm available P (Olsen method), and exchangeable cations Ca 34.5, Mg 2.36, K 0.38, and Na 0.89 meq/100 g soil. Basal fertilizer was 100-50 kg NK/ha. Rice seedlings (IR8 and IR6) were transplanted at 3 wk, 4 seedlings/pot, in a randomized block design with 5 treatments and 4 replications. Plant samples were dried, digested, and analyzed for N, P, K, Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu 10 wk after transplanting.

Plant growth parameters and nutrient content at different levels of P.

P level (kg/ha)	Dry matter yield (g/pot)	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Macronutrients (% dry wt)			Micronutrients (µg/g dry wt)			
				N	P	K	Fe	Mn	Zn	Cu
<i>IR8</i>										
0	11.25	55	7.3	2.23	0.25	2.46	49.7	40.7	114	4.63
40	15.19	80	8.5	2.47	0.27	2.57	57.3	48.5	94	6.00
80	21.75	100	12.7	2.70	0.27	2.85	76.0	52.6	79	5.80
120	27.34	110	16.8	2.85	0.30	2.97	95.0	60.0	71	5.23
160	34.25	115	20.5	2.90	0.31	2.88	125.0	76.3	48	10.43
LSD (0.05)	1.46	9	7.3	0.08	0.06	0.06	13.4	7.6	7	0.81
<i>IR6</i>										
0	6.35	35	5.8	1.95	0.21	2.13	70.0	48.3	121	6.60
40	10.43	53	7.5	2.18	0.22	2.23	87.7	57.4	91	7.30
80	15.74	69	11.2	2.33	0.25	2.45	108.8	65.7	84	9.10
120	22.69	78	14.7	2.41	0.25	2.59	187.7	81.0	69	13.40
160	29.21	100	18.9	2.53	0.26	2.67	227.8	98.0	36	9.30
LSD (0.05)	1.25	6	7.1	0.06	0.05	0.06	9.1	5.8	8	1.16

Dry matter, plant height, and number of tillers increased significantly with increasing P (see table). IR8 had higher response.

Concentrations of all elements were in the ranges considered adequate for plant

growth. Concentrations of N, P, K, Fe, Cu, and Mn increased significantly with P. P level depressed Zn uptake.

Concentrations of N, P, K, Fe, Mn, and Zn were significantly higher in IR8 than in IR6 at all P levels. □